
FACEBOOK ADDICTION AND SPORTS PARTICIPATION AMONG STUDENTS OF TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN JIGAWA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study determined the relationship between the frequency/duration of Facebook utilization and Physical Activity level of students. The participants of the study consisted of students from five tertiary institutions in Jigawa State. Accidental sampling was used to draw the participants from various institutions. It was conducted using a survey design with the use of questionnaire. The findings indicated those students' frequency and duration of time spent using Facebook was higher than their engagement in physical activity during evening sports/games. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended for the need of adequate provision of sports facilities and equipment should be a priority by the authorities of tertiary institutions, need of more strategies for enhancing participation in physical activities and sports by the Sports Directorate and the Guidance and Counseling Units of tertiary institutions.

Keywords: Facebook, Physical Activity, Sports, Participation, Tertiary Students

Introduction

In today's society, Facebook attracts individuals of almost all ages, particularly the adolescents and youths who are mostly at the tertiary level of education. Facebook addiction is increasing in this current era (Omar et al., 2023). Chaffey (2020) reported that more than half of the world uses social media; 4.57 billion people around the world use the internet. In the past, students used to engage in various forms of sports activities especially during leisure hours. But, today with the advent of Facebook, students are less likely to engage in sports and physical activities. In most instances, students spent most of their leisure hours on Facebook chatting and viewing of picture and videos. Omar et al. (2023) revealed that Internet is being widely used all around the world. The number of users is increasing day by day. For example, the usage of Internet and other social networks has increased globally with 82% with an average of 5 and half hours spend on Internet and other social networks. Consequently, Internet addiction disorder can be defined by a need to "escape from oneself," which may account for the excessive using of Internet.

In Nigeria, for example, twenty million five hundred and thirty thousand (20530 000) people are Facebook users as of March 2019, which accounted for 9.8 of its entire population. The majority of them were men 62 %. People aged 25 to 34 were the largest user group (7 100 000) (Napoleon, 2020). In his study, Dule (2023) reported that Facebook has become the leading means of interaction, especially among university students. Despite its usage as the bridge of connection, it is considered an emerging challenge in different aspects, especially among the young generation and tertiary students such as university students, partly because of its heavy and aimless usage. The users are currently increasing, controlling the detrimental effects of Facebook is becoming more challenging, especially in developing countries with unconfirmed regulatory policies (Dule, 2023).

Addiction or over use of Facebook, might likely be linked with physical inactivity and or lack of sports participation among the users or students particularly at tertiary institutions where much freedom is given to the students in their daily activities. This may also be associated with certain risks emanating from the over-use of Facebook, such as insufficient sports participation. However, it is well documented that exercise and sports activities are both physically and psychologically beneficial to human health (Omar et al., 2023). In the medical field, addiction is defined as an extreme craving for and commitment to something, either physically or psychologically. In the current era, internet addiction is the main emerging technology addiction. Serving as ways of connection among people, addiction to the internet and social media like Facebook and others has become a pandemic globally (Dule, 2023).

Individuals who spent 8.5 to 21.5 hours online per week are considered to be addicted (Şahin, 2018). Facebook addiction is linked with lower engagement in physical activity and sports participation. Sahin and Lok (2018) reported that the lower the level of physical activity, the higher is the internet addiction.

The term addiction involves not only the use of substances like drugs or alcohol. It also includes practices or habits that are not controllable. Therefore, Facebook addiction is considered as a kind of internet addiction (Şahin, 2018). Chaffey (2020) revealed that of those social media users, 346 million new users have come online within the last 12 months and 5.15 billion unique mobile users. Of that number, roughly 3.5 billion or 45% of the world's population were active social media users in January 2019. Each year, the figure increases by 9%. The use of Social Media (SM) frequently by young adults has increased to 97% in the year 2016 (Shimoga, Erlyana & Rebello, 2019). For example, Facebook is one of the SM and is estimated to have more than 500 million members (in the year 2013), with the average user

spending more than 20 minutes a day on the site. Facebook ranks as the most used site among students of tertiary institutions to the extent that it would be difficult to find students who were not Facebook users (Zaremohzzabieh et al., 2014).

Dau (2015) investigated the impact of social media addiction among the students of tertiary institutions in Northern Nigeria and the level at which students are addicted. Findings from the study showed that majority of the respondents use almost all popular social media platforms with Facebook having the largest number of users. It was also found that the majority of the respondents use these social media platforms, mainly for social needs such as friendship and dating.

Statement of the problem

Nowadays, Facebook attracts individuals of almost all ages, particularly the adolescents and youths who are mostly at the tertiary level of education. In the past, students used to engage in various forms of sports activities especially during leisure hours. But, today with the advent of Facebook, students are less likely to engage in sports and physical activities. In most instances, students spent most of their leisure hours on Facebook and other social media.

Facebook addicted students reported anxiety and depressive symptoms which are detrimental to health. On the other hand, engagement in sports activities have been shown to significantly improve these symptoms. Facebook ranks as the most used site among students of tertiary institutions to the extent that it would be difficult to find students who were not Facebook users (Zaremohzzabieh et al., 2014).

Concept of Addiction

There are many view regarding the concept by different scholars. Addiction is a medical condition characterized by compulsive engagement in rewarding stimuli, despite adverse consequences (Omar et al., 2023). It is considered a disorder of the brain's reward system which arises through transcriptional and epigenetic mechanisms and occurs over time from chronically high levels of exposure to an addictive stimulus. Both behavioral and substance addictions have many similarities in natural history, phenomenology, and adverse consequences (Omar et al., 2023).

Influence of Facebook on sports and Physical activity

Facebook as part of internet might lead to several influences on sports participation. Numerous studies supported the findings of other studies regarding the impact of Facebook on physical activity and sports participation. For instance, Omar et al. (2023) revealed that being addicted to sports may absorb most of the time and energy of the person and compensate him psychologically and in physically and mentally healthy ways than to be indulging and spending the time and effort in Internet (Facebook) in a pathological addictive way. In their study, Omar et al. (2023) revealed 67.2% of the students who were addicted to Facebook. Their finding appeared to be higher than in the previous studies. This is because their study was conducted recently, a higher level of Facebook addiction is expected as evidence indicating the increasing use of social media in the current era. Sports and physical exercise programs can be combined with existing intervention strategies or pharmacological treatment for Internet addiction in which Facebook inclusive (Omar et al., 2023).

It was reported that extensive use of Facebook is related to behavioral disturbances and poor academic performance among university students, which influences their ways of life and interactions with others. On the other hand, Facebook addiction has been directly linked to

anxiety and depression among university students and has impacted their social lives and mental well-being (Dule, 2023). Anxiety and depression are factors that affect or might likely prevent an individual in sports participation. But on the other hand, participation or engagement in sports and physical activity is non-pharmacological therapy in the treatment of these conditions as revealed by many investigators.

Sports and physical exercise programs can be combined with existing intervention strategies or pharmacological treatment for Internet addiction in which Facebook is inclusive (Omar et al., 2023). So, sports might be considered in a way a healthy addictive behavior that can replace the pathological one.

Shimoga, Erlyana and Rebello (2019) revealed that physically active students with frequent social media usage were associated more with vigorous daily exercises. On the other hand, sedentary students with frequent social media usage were associated with a lower level of vigorous daily exercise. For moderately active students who used social media once or twice a month, they were associated with the highest levels of vigorous daily exercises. Therefore, moderate intensity of social media usage was associated with the highest levels of physical activity engagement.

Facebook addiction is linked with lower engagement in physical activity and sports participation. Sahin and Lok (2018) reported that the lower the level of physical activity, the higher is the internet addiction. A number of negative health outcomes are associated with Facebook addiction among adolescents of which physical inactivity is among. Higher levels of Facebook usage are associated with lower levels of participation in sports and other physical activities (Shimoga et al., 2019), which is detrimental to human health. In another study on the relationship between physical activity and Facebook addiction, it was found that an increase in physical activity among students reduced the phenomenon of internet or Facebook addiction (Sahin & Lok, 2018). Numerous other studies conducted in different countries revealed that Facebook addiction is not only limited to higher students of colleges or universities, but also secondary school and high school students. Individuals who spend 8.5 to 21.5 hours online per week are considered to be addicted (Şahin, 2018).

A particular study has shown that students with high Facebook addiction had disturbed social interactions and relationships that could affect their future careers (Dule, 2023). Khan, Shabbir and Rajput (2017) demonstrated that the frequency of internet addiction was significantly higher for students who lacked any form of intense physical activity compared to those who were intense in physical activity. Sports participation had a significant influence on internet addiction mediated by self-control (Park et al., 2016).

As studies revealed, extended use of Facebook has led to decreased face-to-face contact, sleep disruptions, and mental health disturbances also poor academic performance, and bullying activities, Log-in-related distractions such as uploading, commenting, and chatting with friends are leading to procrastination of learning activities and sinking academic success among university students currently (Dule, 2023).

Facebook has become a global phenomenon and being one of the greatest importance means of communication (Zaremohzzabieh et al., 2014). However, despite the popularity of Facebook due to the great increase in use, speed, interactivity, and free Internet access, an amount of the student user population experiences some negative effects of excessive Facebook usage or are already captured in the 'web' of addiction. At this point it can be realized that university students remain a critical and unsafe position in terms of Facebook addiction. Because social networking sites take as an important part of their daily life and

they provide a lot of helps to university students not only for a social purpose but also for educational purposes. Spending more and more time on Facebook unintentionally raise the chance of addiction in terms of Facebook use. It is required for students for the aspect of knowledge-based society to improve their capability in using technology for putting a plan into their work in a technological setting (Nalwa & Anand, 2003). Conversely, scholars concern about the consequences of alarming rate of mental and addiction and the problems related to heavy use of Facebook among university students (Zaremohzzabieh et al., 2014).

These results could be supporting the idea of being addictive to sports may absorb most of the time and energy of the person and compensate him psychologically and in physically and mentally healthy ways than to be indulging and spending the time and effort in video gaming and Internet in a pathological addictive way.

Methodology for the Study

Jigawa state has the following tertiary institutions namely Jigawa State College of Education, Gumel, Jigawa State College of Legal and Islamic Studies, Ringim, Sule Lamido University, Kafin Hausa. Federal University Dutse., Federal University of technology Babura, Jigawa State Polytechnic Dutse, Hussaini Adamu Federal Polytechnic Kazaure, Jigawa State College of Nursing and Midwifery Birnin Kudu Bilyaminu Usman College of Agriculture Hadejia and Jigawa State School of Health Technology Jahun.

The participants of this study were selected from five tertiary institutions of Jigawa State. Multi-stage sampling techniques was applied using purposive, and accidental sampling to draw the participants of this study. It was conducted using survey design with the use of questionnaire Scale adapted from Sahin (2018), Arslan and Kırık (2013) and International Physical Activity Questionnaire. One (1) institution from the five (5) emirate councils of the state Jigawa State were selected using purposive sampling process to select fifty participants from each institution to obtained 250 participants.

Results

Table 1: Participants' Physical Characteristics

Male	N	%	M±SD
Age	50	27.9	17.71± 2.6
16 – 20	129	62.1	22.47± 3.2
21- 25	21	10.0	24.37± 3.5
26 – 30			
N – 218			

One hundred and twenty nine of the students (62.1%) were within the age range of twenty one to twenty five (21 – 25). This was followed by the students (27.9%) between the ages of sixteen to twenty years (16 – 20). With the few or least (10.0 %) of the students from the age category between 26 to 30 years.

Table 2: Facebook Usage across Areas of Specialization

Facebook	Yes	%	No	%
Arts	58	26.6	14	6.7
Sciences	56	25.6	6	2.9
Languages	67	31.1	7	3.4
N (218)				

From this it can be observed that the undergraduate students of Jigawa state tertiary institutions specializing in Languages courses had the higher frequency with 31.1% of Facebook usage, while those students specializing in Arts courses were 58 representing 26.6% comes second, with the lowest from those specializing in science course that had 26.9% in relation to utilization of Facebook. Even though, there were negligible disparities between the areas of specialization in terms of Facebook use among the undergraduate students from varied areas of specialization.

Table 3: Frequency and Duration of Physical Activity (Sports) and Facebook Usage Regardless of Areas of Specialization

Variable	n	%
Frequency of Physical Activity per week		
Not at all	161	73.8
Once a week	21	9.6
Twice a week	11	5.0
Thrice a week	6	2.7
Four times a week	8	3.6
Five times a week	5	2.2
Every day	6	2.7
Duration of Physical Activity per day		
10 minutes	167	76.6
20 minutes	25	11.4
30 minutes	17	7.7
1 hour	9	4.1
Frequency on Facebook Per Week		
Not at all	13	5.9
Once a week	06	2.7
Twice a week	07	3.2
Thrice a week	19	8.7
Four times a week	28	12.8
Five times a week	34	15.5
Every day	111	50.9
Duration Spent on Facebook Per Day		
10 minutes	17	7.7
20 minutes	08	3.6
30 minutes	10	4.5
1 hour	13	5.9
2 – 5 hours	31	14.2
6 hours and above	139	63.7
N (218)		

The result of table have shown that majority of the students one hundred and sixty one (161) representing 73.8% claimed to have not engage in any physical activity (particularly evening sports/games). The students who revealed to have engaged in physical activity once in a week were only twenty one (9.6%). Those that were capable to participate in physical activity twice in a week were eleven (11) 5.0%. The students that engaged in physical activity for four times in a week are eight (3.6%). Likewise, 2.2% claimed to have participated in physical activity five times a week. Those that engaged in physical activity every day were only 2.7%. From the table it can be noted that the students had inadequate frequency in participation of physical activity. This indicated that the students' frequency for engagement in physical activity did not meet up with the recommended guidelines for the frequency of physical activity.

With regard to the duration or time spent on physical activity per day, the table have shown that majority (76.6 %) reported to have been engaged in physical activity for ten minutes per day only, 11.4% of them for twenty minutes per day, 7.7% for thirty minutes per day, with least of them (4.1%) that engaged for one hour per day.

While, the frequency for the Facebook used, one hundred and eleven of the students revealed to have been online particularly on Facebook every day. This was followed by the students who claimed to use Facebook for five times in a week representing 15.5%. Those who utilized Facebook four times in a week were twenty-eight (12.8%). The students that revealed to use Facebook three times in a week were 19 in number (8.7 %), 3.2% use it twice in a week, with very few (2.7%) that utilized Facebook once in a week. On the other hand, only 5.3% claimed to have not utilizing Facebook at all.

The table also indicated that one hundred and thirty-nine (139) representing 63.7% claimed to be using Facebook from six (6) hours to above daily or every day. This is followed by the students (14.2%) who reported to be using it for 2 to 5 hours daily. Those who use it for one hour every day were 5.9%, while those who use it for 30 minutes had 4.5%, 3.6% of them used for 20 minutes. And 7.7% who utilized for ten minutes every day.

Discussions

Findings of this study have shown that majority of the students (74%) spent seven hours and above on Facebook every day. This finding is in agrrement with that of Şahin (2018) who stated that individuals who spent 8.5 to 21.5 hours online per week are considered to be addicted. To other investigators like Omar et al. (2023) revealed that addiction or over use of Facebook, might likely be linked with physical inactivity and or lack of sports participation among the users or students particularly at tertiary institutions where much freedom is given to the students in their daily activities. This may also be associated with certain risks emanating from the over-use of Facebook, such as insufficient sports participation. However, it is well documented that exercise and sports activities are both physically and psychologically beneficial to human health (Omar et al., 2023).

In his study, Dule (2023) reported that Facebook has become the leading means of interaction, especially among university students. Despite its usage as the bridge of connection, it is considered an emerging challenge in different aspects, especially among the young generation. and tertiary students such as university students, partly because of its heavy and aimless usage. The users are currently increasing, controlling the detrimental effects of Facebook is becoming more challenging, especially in developing countries with unconfirmed regulatory policies (Dule, 2023).

Also, the findings indicated that 73.8% of the students did not engage in any form of physical activity (evening sports/games). This is in agreement with Sahin and Lok (2018) who stated that the lower the level of physical activity, the higher the internet addiction.

Numerous other studies supported the findings of this study. For example, Shimoga, Erlyana and Rebello (2019) revealed that physically active students with frequent social media usage were associated more with vigorous daily exercises. On the other hand, sedentary students with frequent social media usage were associated with a lower level of vigorous daily exercise. For moderately active students who used social media once or twice a month, they were associated with the highest levels of vigorous daily exercises. Therefore, moderate intensity of social media usage was associated with the highest levels of physical activity.

The frequency of internet addiction was significantly higher for students who lacked any form of intense physical activity compared to those who were intense in physical activity (Khan, Shabbir & Rajput, 2017). Sports participation had a significant influence on internet addiction mediated by self-control (Park et al., 2016).

Recommendations

Based on the finding of this study, the following recommendations were proffered:

- There is need for the youths to be educated on the proper usage of Internet and the Facebook.
- Adequate provision of sports facilities and equipment should be a priority by the authorities of tertiary institutions.
- Provision of mass awareness on the negative influence of Facebook addiction by Sports Directorate and the Guidance and Counseling Units of tertiary institutions.

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